

SELECT NEWSPAPERS' COVERAGE OF THE THREE LEADING CANDIDATES IN THE FEBRUARY 25, 2023 PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION IN NIGERIA

Okoye Jude Vitalis Chukwudi and Prof. Venatus Nosike Agbanu

Department of Mass Communication, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria.

E-mail: okoyejvc@gmail.com, okoyejudevc2018@gmail.com/ venagbanu@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024118>

Abstract: *This study examines select newspapers' coverage of the three leading candidates in the 8 months period running up to the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria. Guided by the Agenda setting and Framing theories, the study used Content analysis design to achieve three objectives, namely: ascertain the prominence given to the news stories published on the presidential candidates; the frequency of coverage of the candidates and the slants of the news stories on each presidential candidate. Using the composite week sampling technique and the systematic random sampling procedure, the study sourced 674 news stories from 200 samples obtained from a population of 1210 editions of five purposely selected newspapers, including: This Day, Guardian, Punch, Sun, and Leadership newspapers. The study found frequency and prominence of coverage to be high and adequate for all the candidates with the candidate of the APC obtaining the highest frequency of coverage, (35.16%), followed by the candidate of the PDP (33.53%), and the candidate of the LP (31.30%). Again, the study found that the candidates were positioned prominently in the newspapers (53%) with only 47% of the stories published regarded as not prominent by virtues of their placements and sizes in the pages. Again, the study found that although the candidate of LP secured the least frequency, stories on him were the most prominently positioned during the period under review. The study also found that the presidential candidate of the APC was most negatively slanted (48.2%) and that of the LP most positively slanted (45.3%), while the candidate of the PDP attracted the most neutrally slanted coverage (42.2%). The study concludes that although the frequency and prominence of coverage were high and adequate enough for every candidate and news slants in line with the realities associated with the candidates, but the intended impact of the newspapers' coverage was not absolute. For example, the popularity of the candidate of the LP whose stories were the most positively slanted and prominently positioned never reflected the outcome of the election as opposed to that of the candidate of the APC who emerged winner and whose stories were less prominently positioned and most negatively slanted. The study concludes that media messages competed with pre-determined attitude of the voters and other social factors such as vote buying, religion, ethnicity etc, to influence voter behavior. The study recommends among others things, that the media should always give equal attention to all candidates and be careful in their news slants so as to provide equal playing ground for every candidate.*

Key Words: Newspaper, Coverage, Presidential. Election, Nigeria. 2023.

Introduction

Background

Periodic election no doubt is one of the fundamental components of the democratic process. It provides the citizens with the opportunity to choose their representatives especially when the process is free and fair (Oyovbaire, 1987). Understanding the critical issues during electioneering campaigns is always a challenge to the electorates. This therefore called for a responsible media role for the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria as news coverage of electioneering campaigns not only provides visibility but helps the electorates to make sense out of the many candidates on offer. Media coverage of electioneering campaigns lubricates the political system; create the critical link between the politicians and the citizens as they provide platforms for public debates and exchange of political ideals and ideologies (Atkinson & Krebs, 2008).

News coverage is therefore an important aspect of media representation which concerns how media texts deal with and present social realities to an audience (Boomgaarden, 2017). News coverage can impact and shape particular public beliefs and attitude as well as contribute to social change (Yildiz, et.al, 2022). The image of a candidate in an election is of utmost importance to the success of the candidate if fairly presented to the voters through news coverage (Devaney, 2013). News therefore, have the power to shape audience's understanding of important issues as representations of socio-political phenomena in news coverage help the public to be well informed to take meaningful decisions concerning issues and events that could affect their lives.

Statement of the problem and scope of the study

However, because journalists frame news, offering angles or particular narratives to direct the people to think in a particular way, news coverage is intrinsically connected to the opinions and ideologies of the media producers and or their owners (Agbanu, 2018). Hence, in order to understand media impact on voter behavior in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria, this study comparatively examined select newspapers' coverage of the three major candidates in the eight months period running up to the election in Nigeria.

Millions of Nigerians turn to the newspapers daily for updates on politics, therefore, an understanding of how nationally circulating' newspapers in Nigeria covered the three major presidential candidates could be important in understanding media impact on voter behavior during presidential elections in Nigeria. This is more so as the quantity of reportage, prominence of reportage and news slants in which the candidates were cast could play a role in shaping and influencing voter decision. The study hence, examined the coverage of the candidates of All Peoples Congress (the APC), Peoples Democratic Party (the PDP) and Labour Party (the LP) by five purposively selected newspapers, including: *This-Day*, *Leadership*, *The Sun*, *The Punch* and *The Guardian* newspapers.

The choice of these newspapers was justified with respect to their wide circulation and by their geographical locations, ownership, and ethno-religious and political affiliations.

Research objectives

While the general objective was the examining of the framing in the news of the three major candidates, the specific objectives were:

1. To ascertain the select newspapers' frequency of coverage of the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.
2. To ascertain the prominence given to the news stories the select newspapers published on the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.
3. To understand the slants of the news stories published by the select newspapers on the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Research Questions

Deriving from the objectives this study sourced data and answered the following research questions:

1. What are the select newspapers' frequencies of coverage of the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria?
2. Did the select newspapers give prominent positioning (above 40%) to the news stories on the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria?
3. What are the slants of the news stories published by the select newspapers on the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria?

Review of related literature

Secondary sources including textbooks, journal articles, internet sources, and other publications provided related materials for review.

Theoretical frameworks

- (1) Agenda setting theory. (2) Framing theory.

The agenda setting theory: formally propounded by McComb and Shaw (1972) has the basic assumption that the media set public agenda by predetermining the importance media consumers placed on news topics through quantity and prominence of reportage and the number of controversies generated in the text. The theory describes the ability of the news media to influence the importance the audience exposed to the same media messages placed on the topics of the news stories (McCombs and Reynolds, 2002), suggesting that the mass media texts have the ability to shape public opinion driven by mass media's bias on topics such as politics, etc.,. Hence media shape public opinion by determining what issues are given the most attention or prominence in the news. Agenda setting implies that the mass media pre-determine what issues the audiences are to regard as important at a given time in a given society by making those issues visible and striking (McCombs and Shaw, 1972).

Public issues or party candidates are usually the units of analysis in agenda setting based investigations, but beyond this, there exists a second level of agenda setting: the attribute agenda

(McCombs & Reynolds, 2009). This is to say that each of the objects on an agenda has many attributes or characteristics that describe them. As objects on agenda vary in salience so do their attributes. Both the selection of objects for attention and the selection of attributes for picturing the objects are powerful agenda setting roles. An important part of the news agenda is the attributes that journalists and subsequently, members of the public have in mind when they think and talk about each object. These attributes (i.e., different aspects of issues) are emphasized to varying degrees in the news to influence how people think and talk about the issues (McCombs & Reynolds, 2009). This is the link between agenda setting and the idea of news framing, in that both show the various ways journalists and their audiences view daily news stories.

Media framing theory: propounded by Goffman (1974) has the basic assumption that media producers organize peoples' experiences (how they make sense) of social realities in news reports by constructing news angles or selective narratives using words, images and contexts (Agbanu , 2018). It deals with the idea of creating or constructing news angles and selective narratives or perspectives of an event by journalists to achieve an end using words, contexts and footages. "It is a way of giving an overall interpretation to isolated items of facts, when journalists shape and contextualize the facts of news stories within some familiar frame of reference".

Literature on framing theory shows that journalists do not only offer objective and balanced coverage of the facts of events and issues but also unconsciously construct narrative structures/perspectives that direct the thinking of media consumers on these events, meaning that framing theory suggests that the way journalists' present and define information about events and issues for the audience (called "the frame") influences the sense media consumers make about that information (Tewksbury and Scheufele, 2009; Gitlin, 1980; McCombs, 2004, pg. 87; Entman, 2007, 1993, pg. 52; Schuefele and Iyengar, 2014; de Vreese, 2000). de Vreese (2005) explains that framing involves a communication source presenting and defining an issue, with emphasis in salience of the different aspects of the issue as each issue or policy being described has attributes (different aspects) that characterize it. Explaining further, de Vreese (2005) says that frames in the news can take the forms of journalists' descriptions of people and other political objects including their choice of the elements of events to include in the news and choice of words and images used to name an issue, etc. As a result, news stories become constructions of realities as well as issue packages aimed at influencing the public understanding of events and issues in a particular way. While the agenda setting function gears towards issue visibility (through coverage in terms of message displays/placements, frequency, prominence and conflicts generated), media framing function goes beyond and deeper into the text to select, filter and emphasize saliency of elements or attributes that characterize the objects (issue or topic) of media agenda (Tewksbury and Scheufele, 2009; deVreese, 2005).

Three ways through which journalists achieve framing in news reportage (Agbanu (2018) include:

1. By using or avoiding certain key words in a news story

2. By playing up an aspect or attribute of an issue or event while downplaying others.
3. By including some items as facts by using words to signify them, and excluding some items as non-facts when reporting a specific news event.

Media framing and Agenda setting theories hence embody propositions, constructs and definitions that give overview of media representation framework in the political process; hence they seem appropriate as study guides and helped in the selection of this study's unit of analysis and construction of the content categories.

Media Coverage

The mass media play a central role for the functioning of modern democracy (Ibraheem et.al, 2015). Media role concerns how information about events and issues in society are defined, presented and interpreted to the public. In performing this traditional role, the media represent realities and, in the process, set public agenda (McCombs & Shaw, 1972; McCombs and Reynolds, 2009), and influence the public to think in certain ways and hold certain opinion about issues and events (de Vreese, et.al, 2001; Tewksbury & Scheufele, 2009). Media coverage provides facts and figures which are crucial for public belief, attitude and decision making in the political process (Oyovbaire, 1987). This is because the meanings/interpretations the media allocate to events and issues help shape public perceptions and constitute a vital ingredient of the democratic process. Information is a lubricant in the democratic process and its importance is like what water is to fish (Akinfeleye, 2007).

In performing their traditional news functions in democracy media coverage provides visibility to issues and help to allocate meanings to them (McCombs & Shaw, 1972; McCombs and Reynolds, 2009; de Vreese, et.al, 2001; Tewksbury & Scheufele, 2009).

In media coverage, journalists construct a reality from a particular perspective, with each narrative constructed containing certain patterns of value judgments whose logic stems from the view of the role of language in social life (Chiluwa & Chiluwa, 2022). This view holds that meaning is not necessarily embedded in reality as we perceive it, but that meaning is constructed through language use, and language use in texts (or talks) invariably assigns meaning to persons, events and situations in a particular way that suits the objectives of the language user. Hence, media texts are constructed, being value judgments made about social realities and relationships that mirror the position and purpose of their producers, reflecting in the choices media producers make about what is left in the background, included or excluded, made explicit or left implicit in the text (Chiluwa, 2011).

Media coverage and ideology

Ideology refers to public beliefs or attitudes shared by members of a particular social group which may not always be consciously held by individuals, but can be deeply rooted in their thought patterns and language that it is taken for granted as self-evident and hence very difficult to question and hard to challenge openly in the social arena (Bloor and Bloor, 2007, pg.10).

Ideological position can be hidden by the use of words and how issues, individuals or groups are represented in media coverage have been shown to be a function of underlying ideological perceptions, meaning that ideological work of media language includes representing issues, individuals or groups, identities and relations in media coverage (Chiluwa, 2011). However, some particular representations in press coverage may conceal truths that need to be told and may legitimize particular negative labeling or identity in the interest of certain people or government (Dijk, 2005).

Media coverage of politics

Journalists as media gatekeepers decide which information, ideologies, or political candidates that enter the news channels, receive prominence in positive or negative tones (McQuail, 2010; Barzinlai-Nahon, 2008). In performing this gatekeeper's function for the political system journalists must be fair, balanced and objective in news coverage as the quality of information the electorates get during elections depends on how best journalists follow these principles in their news selection exercises (McGregor, 2010). This indicates that biased coverage of issues in politics could have unpalatable consequences for the democratic process as citizens are likely to decide wrongly which could retard the optimum performance of the political system. Consequently, news has become crucial in democracy because balanced and fair coverage of all issues, parties, aspirants and manifestoes is key to guiding the electorates to choose the right political leaders (Boomgaarden, 2017).

The newspaper medium

Newspaper is an aspect of the mass media outside of television, radio, cinema and the internet and alongside other printed matter is referred to as the press, taken from its major technology, the printing press (Amobi & Hussein, 2013). Newspapers exist as vital information sources about local, national and international political events, including presidential campaigns (Benoit, et.al. 2015). The press has always specialized on human interest stories, in dramatic and sensational styles of reporting and presentation (McQuail, 2010). The "elite" press, independent from the state and from vested interests was recognized as a major institution of political and social life, especially as a self-appointed former of public opinion and voice of national interest and tended to show a highly developed sense of social and ethical responsibility, fostering the rise of journalistic profession dedicated to balanced, fair and objective reporting of issues and events (ibid).

Major Candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election

The candidate of the PDP: Atiku Abubakar, Muslim, retired custom officer, former vice president, businessman, politician was born on 25 November 1946 in Jada, Adamawa state, northern Nigeria.

The candidate of the APC: Bola Ahmed Adegunle Tinubu, Muslim, accountant, former senator and former governor of Lagos state, was born on 29 March 1954 in Lagos South-western Nigeria. APC currently is the ruling party.

The candidate of the LP: Peter Gregory Obi, Christian, businessman and politician, born on July 9, 1961 in Onitsha, Anambra State, was in May 2022. Obi was the former governor of Anambra with an “ideology of frugality; economic and resourceful management. LP had a deficient or nonexistent party structure. However, Obi's attracted followers nationwide, especially younger Nigerians.

Methodology

The study design was content analysis. It directed data collections, measurements and analysis, as it dealt with the arrangement of conditions and analysis of data (Kothari & Garg, 2016). Content analysis design helped to focus on the manifest contents of newspapers (Robin, et.al, 2005; Sobawale, 2008).

Area of study

This study was conducted in the South east Nigeria focusing on the national newspapers circulated in the zone during the period under review.

Population of study

The population of study is 1210 editions of five purposively select newspapers. Nigeria has a total of 28 national daily newspapers in circulation (Aladi and Okoro, 2020). The select newspapers include: *This Day*, *Leadership*, *The Punch*, *The Sun* and *The Guardian* Newspapers. The choice of these newspapers was with respect to their large circulation geographical locations, ownership, ethno-religious and political affiliations. The study covered 8 months period spanning from June, 2022 to February 2023. These account for 242 editions each of the five newspapers understudy, summing up to a total of 1210 editions in all.

Sampling procedure and Sample size

The study sampled using the Jones and Carter (1959) **constructed composite weeks sampling technique**. This sampling technique has been adopted in a related study by Aladi and Okoro (2020). In this regard, the study randomly selected 5 days from each month. Hence 5 days per month for 8 months summed up to 40 days per newspaper (for five newspapers). This amounts to 200 editions in all.

News reports examined in the study were obtained from sampled editions randomly and systematically from all the selected newspapers on equal proportion using the **probability sampling procedure** so that every member in the population had an equal chance of being selected. The **systematic sampling technique with a random selection** using the **balloting system** was employed. The technique operates on the basis of the first element being randomly selected. The study used **number 6 as the Nth point. This means that every 6th edition of the select newspapers was systematically selected starting from a point that was determined by ballot**. The first element determined who the other elements were. Thus, the sample size amounted to 201.666666 newspapers, approximately **200**.

Content category and units of analysis

The units of analysis are the presidential candidates of the APC, the PDP and the LP, while content categories are as indicated below:

Category 1. Prominence: In this category, the study is interested in the placement of the story and the kind of attention given to the story in terms of the headline and the space occupied in the newspapers. Relying on this, stories concerning the three presidential candidates in the 2023 election published in the front and back page of the newspapers are regarded as very prominence while those inside the pages of the newspapers with small headline and minor space are classified as not prominence. On the other hand, news stories concerning the three presidential candidates in the 2023 election published inside the newspaper with big headline otherwise called inside page lead story are classified as prominence.

Category 2, Frequency of coverage: on the content category of frequency, the study is interested in the number of times the media understudy published stories on the presidential candidates. Consequently, the candidate who is on the news most frequently will be adjudged as having a high frequency of news published.

Category 3: Slant of news stories: The units under the category are three. Favorable, neutral and unfavorable. Stories are classified as favorable if such story is seeing the presidential candidates from being in line with the ideal situation that the country should be. It is unfavorable if the story condemns the side approach the candidate prescribes to solve the country's problem and neutral when the story is neither for nor against the candidate.

Instrument of data Collection, Validity and Reliability

Data collection instrument was coding sheet. The coding guide and sheet were subjected to the scrutiny and constructive criticisms, corrections and suggestions on the structure and content of the instruments to strengthen it to be able to measure what it was designed to measure. The instrument was further subjected to inter-coder reliability test to ascertain its correlation coefficient to establish its consistency in measuring items set to be examined. Inter-coder reliability was assessed using Holsti's inter-coder reliability formula. The Holsti's inter coder reliability test was calculated thus:

Reliability:

$$R = \frac{2(M)}{N_1 + N_2}$$

$$N_1 + N_2$$

Where:

M= the number of coding decisions which two coders agree.

N1 & N2= the number of coding decisions by the first and second coder respectively.

Therefore, Inter-coder reliability

$$R = \frac{2(34)}{68}$$

$$49 + 38 = 87$$

$$= 0.78$$

Method of data analysis

Data were presented in tables and simple percentages with the implications of the data explained under. All thematic data were analyzed descriptively against the research questions. Data were used to supply answers to the research questions posed for the study through which the conclusion and recommendations were drawn.

Data presentation and analysis

Data were presented and analyzed using frequency distribution tables, simple percentages, mean scores and other simple statistical tools.

Table 1: Monthly distribution of stories on the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria

Monthly	<i>This-Day</i>	<i>Leadership</i>	<i>The sun</i>	<i>Punch</i>	Guardian	Freq.	%
June	10	16	11	15	13	65	9.6
July	19	13	21	14	12	79	11.7
August	13	12	12	10	11	58	8.6
September	10	11	13	14	12	60	8.9
October	27	12	16	12	14	81	12.0
November	24	9	18	28	15	94	13.9
December	15	11	12	22	10	70	10.3
January	36	24	18	21	15	114	16.9
February	10	8	10	15	10	53	7.8
Total	164	116	131	151	112	674	100

Source: Researcher’s content analysis 2024

Table 1 shows the monthly distribution of the news stories on the three presidential candidates in the 8 months period under review. The data revealed that the *This-Day* newspaper with a total of 164 news stories out of 674 news stories was on the lead in the coverage. This figure represents 24.33% of the total number of news stories published. This is followed by the *Punch* newspaper which published 151 news stories representing 22.40% of the total publications. *The Leadership*, *The Guardian*, and *The Sun*, newspapers published 116 (17.21%), 112 (16.61%) and 131 (19.43%) respectively. Data also indicate that the month of January 2023 dominated in the number of publications, during the period under review with 114 stories (16.91%) out of the 674 published. Data showed a zigzag pattern of publications in all the newspapers under review, from the month of June 2022 to the month of February 2023 when the election was conducted. The zigzag pattern of publications indicates that the newspapers performed more jobs in the month of January when the political tempo in the country became very high with expectations.

Table 2: Average distribution of stories on the three major candidates among the select newspapers in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria

Newspapers	Total average pages Per day	Average number of main stories per page	Total average main stories per day	Total main stories in a month	Total main stories in 8 months	Number on the three presidential candidates	Total % covered in 8 months
This-Day	56	5	280	8400	67,200	164	0.24
Leadership	44	5	220	6600	52,800	116	0.21
The sun	60	6	360	10800	86,400	131	0.15
The punch	56	6	336	10080	80,640	151	0.18
Guardian	46	5	230	6900	55,200	112	0.20
TOTAL	262	27	1,326	35,880	342,240	674	0.98

Source: Researcher’s contents analysis, 2024

Table 2 shows the general news items published by the five select newspapers in the period understudy. Data indicate that a total of 342,240 stories were published. Out of this total, 674 news stories representing 0.98% were published on the three presidential candidates alone. The table thus implied that the three presidential candidates commanded media attention in Nigerian within the period under review.

Table 3: Frequency of representation of the three major candidates in the select newspapers in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria within the period of study

Variables	<i>This-Day</i>	<i>Leadership</i>	<i>The sun</i>	<i>Punch</i>	Guardian	Freq	%
APC	53	51	45	54	34	237	35.1
LP	67	27	40	50	27	211	31.3
PDP	44	38	46	47	51	226	33.5
Total	164	116	131	151	112	674	100

Source: Researcher’s contents analysis 2024

Data in Table 3 demonstrate that of all the three political candidates, the candidate of APC was most frequently covered by the newspapers accounting for 35.1% of the total publications on the presidential candidates made in the five newspapers. This left the candidate of the LP at the bottom of the table with a total of 211 stories representing 31.3% of the stories. The reason for the data in Table 3 cannot be divorced from the fact that APC is the leading party coupled with the issue of Muslim-

Muslim ticket which made the party more on the media as different people are on the media space to canvass for or against the ticket.

Table 4: Showing whether the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria were given prominent coverage by the select newspapers

Placement of stories	<i>APC</i>	<i>LP</i>	<i>PDP</i>	Freq	%
Front page	52(21.9)	61(28.9)	57(25.2)	170	25.2
Inside page	117(49.3)	94(44.5)	108(47.7)	319	47.3
Inside page lead story	64(27.0)	54(25.5)	57(25.2)	175	25.9
Back page	4(1.6)	2(0.9)	4(1.7)	10	1.4
TOTAL	237	211	226	674	100

Source: Researcher’s contents analysis 2024

Data in table 4 show the placement of the stories in the coverage of the three presidential candidates in the 2023 election in Nigeria. Data indicate the candidate of the LP is most prominently covered with 28.9% of the total front page news stories published. This is followed by the candidate of the People’s Democratic Party (PDP), with 25.2% of the front-page news stories. The candidate of All Progressive Alliance (APC) occupied the third position with 21.9% in all. While the candidate of the LP gathered 55.3% of the stories placed in front page, inside lead stories and back page, the candidate of the PDP secured 52.1% leaving the candidate of the APC with 50.5% of the stories in the same category. Again, data in Table 4 show that among the stories positioned inside the news pages with less significant placement and prominent value, the candidate of the APC has a total of 49.3% followed by the candidate of the PDP who scored 47.7% and the candidate of the LP with 44.5%. This implies that although the candidate of the APC got the highest number of stories published within the period, the candidate of LP received the most prominent positioning on the focal points of the newspapers. In general, the media did well in providing details of their coverage of the three candidates in the election. Considering the placement of the stories on the three candidates in the newspaper, table 4 has shown that inside page stories with less prominent values secured only 47.3% of the total 674 stories published in the newspaper within the period covered in the study.

Table 5: Slant of news representation of the three major candidates in the media in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria

Slant of stories	<i>APC</i>	<i>LP</i>	<i>PDP</i>	Freq	%
Favorable slant	45(31.9)	64(45.3)	32(22.6)	141	20.9
Neutral slant	56(22.3)	89(35.4)	106(42.2)	251	37.2
Unfavorable slant	136(48.2)	58(20.5)	88(31.2)	282	41.8
Total	237	211	226	674	100

Source: Researcher’s contents analysis 2024

Data in Table 5 show that the candidate of the APC was most unfavorably represented in the media. The candidate of the PDP secured the highest neutrally-slanted report while the candidate of the LP enjoyed the highest favorable media coverage controlling 45.3% of the total favorable slants of news reports among the three. The media can be said to have done their works here leaving the people to take the decision on who to vote for in the election.

Answers to Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the frequencies of the select newspapers news reports on each of the three candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria?

Research question number 1 is interested in the number of times the newspapers published news stories on each of the candidates during the period under review. Data in Table 3 indicated that of all the three presidential candidates, the candidate of APC was most frequently reported in the media with 234 stories which represented 35.1% of the total publications made in the five newspapers. This was followed by the candidate of the PDP with 221 stories representing 33.5%, and leaving the candidate of LP at the bottom of the table with a total of 211 stories representing 31.3% of the stories.

Research Question 2: Did the select newspapers give prominent positioning (above 40%) to the news stories on the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria?

Research question two is interested in the placement of the stories and the kind of attention given to the story in terms of the headlines and the spaces occupied in the newspapers. Data tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 demonstrated that the select newspapers within the period under study gave prominence to the coverage of the three presidential candidates. Data in table 4 specifically showed that of all the total number of stories identified and examined only 47.3% were positioned inside the pages without any element of prominence like lead stories or bold headlines, while the remaining stories (52.7%) were in prominent positions in the front and back pages of the select newspapers. In addition, data in table 1 and 2 showed that out of the 342,240 total number of news stories published, 674 news stories representing 0.98% were published on the three presidential candidates alone within this period of 8 months. The table thus implied that the three presidential candidates commanded media attention in Nigerian within the period under review.

Research Question 3: What are the slants of the select newspapers news reports on each of the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria?

Research question 3 sought to ascertain the slant (how favorable, unfavorable or neutral) of the news stories in the coverage of the presidential candidates. Data in Table 5 show that the candidate of the APC was most unfavorably represented in the media (48.2%). The candidate of the PDP secured the highest neutrally-slanted reports (42.2%), while the candidate of the LP, enjoyed the highest favorable media coverage controlling 45.3% of the total favorable slants of news reports among the three.

Discussion of findings

Objective number one sought to find out the frequency/quantity of coverage in the media, the data in Table 2 indicate that the candidates received high frequency of coverage. Out of the total 342,240 stories published during the eight months period 674 stories representing 0.98% was published on the candidates. Data showed that of all the three candidates, the candidate of the APC was mostly frequently covered in the newspapers. This may suggest that the candidate's popularity, pattern of campaign and his party's incumbency may have been instrumental to the attention that the candidate gained from the media. This assertion supports Boomgarden (2017) idea of "incumbency bonus" in political news coverage, which is a particular form of visibility bias which help political candidates and parties in power gain media attention and a higher chance of making it into the news channels. The status of APC as the ruling party at the period under review would have provided its candidate this media bias termed "incumbency bonus"

Objective number two is to ascertain whether the media prominently covered (above 40%) the three presidential candidates. Data indicate that the select newspapers gave prominent positioning to the reports of the three presidential candidates. Data show that out of the total number of stories identified and examined; only 47.3% were positioned inside the pages of the newspapers. The stories were without any element of prominence such as being the lead stories or being given bold headlines. On the other hand, 52.7% of the stories published on the candidates were prominently positioned on the focal points of the newspapers. This higher percentage signifies prominence in the coverage of the candidates by the select newspapers. This finding also signifies intent on the part of the newspapers to set public agenda by highlighting and prominently positioning stories. This finding is also in line with the social responsibility theory of the media which places the media on obligation to inform the public about happenings/events around them. Again, the finding is in line with the surveillance function of the media which helps to checkmate the activities of the political class who controls the policy making process of the state. By prominently providing information about the presidential candidates to the people in the focal points of their pages, the newspapers have done well in delivering their social responsibility duties to the people (See Agudosy, Ikegbunam and Obiakor, 2018).

Moreover, data indicate that although the candidate of the LP has the least of the total number of stories published in his favor, he was more prominently covered/positioned than the other two candidates of the APC and of the PDP based on the percentage of the stories placed on the various focal parts of the newspapers. However, in spite of the prominence given to the candidate of the LP, He secured a distant third position in the election behind the candidates of APC and PDP. This finding tends to justify the criticism of the agenda setting hypothesis and the framing media effect which support the views that although the media has the ability to give the people what to think about (Cohen, 1963); influence the importance attached to media topics and shape the public perceptions of media audience (McComb & Shaw, 1972), it is still within the power of the media consumers to decide whether to adopt the media agenda and framing pattern or not (See Ikegbunam and Agudosy,

2021, Uzochukwu and Ikegbunam, 2022). In the real sense of it, despite being prominently projected the outcome of the election never reflected the popularity of the candidates in the media. This of course goes in line with the generalization of Klapper (1960) which states” that mass communication does not serve as a necessary and sufficient cause of audience effects, but rather functions among and through a nexus of mediating factors and influences...”

On the third research objective which is to ascertain the slant of the news stories published on the three candidates, data indicated that the candidate of the APC was most negatively slanted with 136 stories against him. This was followed by the candidate of PDP with 31.2% of the 282 stories having negative slants. According to the data the candidate with the most positive news slant in his favor is the candidate of the LP who secured a total of 64 stories accounting for 45.2% of the 142 stories found to be positive on the coverage of the three candidates. However, the irony of this situation was that although data showed this pattern of coverage it never reflected in the election’s outcome

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

This study examined the coverage of the three major candidates by select newspapers in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria. The study adopted the content analysis study design and anchored on media framing and agenda setting theories. The study answered three research questions, with each highlighting a different aspect of the manifest content of the newspapers. The study covered a period of 8 months and has the composite sampling week method as its sample selection pattern. A total of 242 days were selected and 200 editions out of 1210 editions were examined. A total of 674 stories out of 342,240 were published on the three major candidates with the number of stories published on the candidates constituting 0.89% of the total publications made. The study found as follows:

1. That the frequency of coverage of the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria by the select newspapers during the eight months period under review was high and adequate. The presidential candidate of the APC obtained the highest frequency of coverage, (35.16%), followed by the candidate of the PDP (33.53%), and the candidate of the LP (31.30%).
2. That news stories on the three major candidates in the February 25, 2023 presidential election in Nigeria were positioned prominently in the newspapers (53%). Only 47% of the stories published on the candidates were regarded as not prominent by virtues of their placements and sizes in the pages.
3. That although the candidate of LP secured the least number of stories published (least frequency), events about him were the most prominently positioned by the five select newspapers during the period under review.

4. That the presidential candidate of the APC was most negatively slanted (48.2%) and that of the LP most positively slanted (45.3%), while the candidate of the PDP attracted the most neutrally slanted coverage (42.2%).

Conclusions

The study concludes that there is a difference in impact between the newspaper's coverage '(framing/or agenda) and public agenda (voter behavior) implying that, in as much as the newspapers had the power to shape the perception of the people on the personalities of the candidates, they could only teach and not coerce the people on who to vote for. This supports the claims among emerging communication scholars that media effect is not absolute as media compete with audience predetermined attitude and other factors in shaping the perceptions and actions on issues. For example, irrespective of achieving a comparatively good quantity of coverage, taking the lead on positive news slants and prominent positioning against the candidates of APC and PDP whose stories were dominated by negative news slants and less prominent positioning, the candidate of the LP placed last position among the three candidates at the poll.

Recommendations

1. The mass media should continue to pay attention and give adequate, equitable and prominent coverage to future presidential candidates in order to help the people take informed decisions on whom to vote for. Doing these makes them to live within the ambit of the social responsibility function as an intermediary between the people and the government.
2. The media should always examine the candidates well before fanning them in order not to project an image that will not reflect the truth to the people. In this regard, emotional laden media slants should be avoided by professionals at all time in the interest of objectivity in media practice.
3. The Nigerian citizens who are exposed to the media messages should at all time premise their decision-making idea on the views and reports covered in the media concerning presidential candidate to avoid regrets after voting.
4. Further investigation should be carried out to ascertain whether there is a significant relationship between the newspapers' coverage of the presidential candidate and actual voter behaviour in the election.

References

- Abegunde, O., & Fajimbola, O. (2018). Media and democratic governance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research-GRANTHAALAYAH*, 6(11), 94-108.
<https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v6.i11.2018.1093>

Michigan International Journal of Marketing, New Media and Communication

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836-9424

Impact Factor: 6.39

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJMNMC>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Agbanu, V. N. (2018). Same event, multiple stories: Framing in international news coverage. In Nwodu & Onunkwo (Eds.), *Evolving thoughts on international communication, diplomacy and the social media*. Enugu: Ryce Kerex Ltd.

Agbanu, V. N. (2015). *Propaganda and public opinion: A discourse on political communication and mind management*. Enugu: Ryce Kerex Ltd.

Agudosi, F. I., Ikegbunam, P. C., & Obiakor, C. U. (2018). Nigerian newspapers coverage of President Buhari's ill health. *The Nigerian Journal of Communication (TNJC)*, 15(2), 335-346.

Akinfeleye, R. (2008). Democracy, the media and national interest. In R. Akinfeleye (Ed.), *Contemporary issues in mass media for development and national security*. Lagos: Malthouse Press Ltd.

Akpoghiran, I. P. (2023). News frames emotion: Analyzing how audience are influenced by news frames. *American Journal of Arts, Social and Humanity Studies*, 3(1), 48-64. ISSN 2959-5827.

Amobi, I. T., & Hussein, S. (2013). *Boko Haram, the media and national security*. Communication Review, 7. University of Lagos: Dept. of Mass Communication.

Aladi, J. A., & Okoro, N. M. (2020). Print media representation of Nigerian women in the news: A study of four selected newspapers. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 3962. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/3962>

Arowolo, S. O. (2017). *Understanding framing theory*. ResearchGate publications.

Atkinson, L. R., & Krebs, T. B. (2008). Press coverage of mayoral candidates: The role of gender in news reporting and campaign issue speech. *Journal of Political Research*, 61(2), 239-252.

Bajracharya, S. (2018). Framing theory. *Businessstopia*. <http://www.businessstopia.net/masscommunication/framing-theory>

Barzilai-Nahon, K. (2008). Towards a theory of network gatekeeping: A framework for exploring information control. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 59(9), 1493-1512. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.20857>

Bateson, G. (1972). *Steps to an ecology of mind: Collected essays in anthropology, psychology, evolution, and epistemology*. San Francisco, CA: Chandler.

Michigan International Journal of Marketing, New Media and Communication

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836-9424

Impact Factor: 6.39

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJMNMC>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Bloor, M., & Bloor, T. (2007). *The practice of critical discourse analysis*. London: Hodder Education.
- Boomgaarden, H. G. (2017). Media representation: Politics. *The International Encyclopedia of Media Effects*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118783764.wbieme0149>
- Chiluwa, I., & Chiluwa, M. I. (2022). 'Deadlier than Boko Haram': Representations of the Nigerian herder–farmer conflict in the local and foreign press. *SAGE Journals*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/175063522090249>
- Chiluwa, I. (2011). Media representation of Nigeria's joint military task force in the Niger Delta crisis. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 1(9), 197.
- de Vreese, C. H. (2005). News framing: Theory and typology. *Information Design Journal + Document Design*, 13(1), 51-62. John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- de Vreese, C. H., Peter, J., & Sementico, H. A. (2001). Framing politics at the launch of the euro: A cross-sectional comparative study of frames in the news. *Political Communication*, 18(2), 107-122.
- Devaney, H. (2013). *Perceptions of media bias: Viewing the news through ideological cues*. A Senior Honor Thesis, University of California, San Diego.
- Drew, C. (2022). *Agenda setting theory (Definitions, examples, and criticisms)*. <https://helpfulprofessor.com/agenda-setting-theory>
- Entman, R. B. (1993). Framing: Toward clarification of a fractured paradigm. *Journal of Communication*, 43, 51–58.
- Gamson, W. A., & Modigliani, A. (1989). Media discourse and public opinion on nuclear power: A constructionist approach. *American Journal of Sociology*, 95, 1-37.
- Gitlin, T. (1980). *The whole world is watching*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Goffman, E. (1974). *Frame analysis: An essay on the organization of experience*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Ibraheem, I. A., Ogwezzy-Ndesikka, O. A., & Tejumaiye, A. (2015). Beyond influence: Media and the 2015 presidential election. Retrieved from www.inecnigeria.org/2015

Michigan International Journal of Marketing, New Media and Communication

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836-9424

Impact Factor: 6.39

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJMNMC>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Ikegbunam, P. C., & Agudosi, F. I. (2021). Cultivating Biafra agenda in Nigeria: Evolution of Radio Biafra's rhetoric of ethnic marginalization on rural dwellers in the South-East. *Journal of Media and Communication Studies*, 13(1), 23-31. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JMCS2020.0698>

Kothari, C. R., & Garg, G. (2016). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.

Lecheler, S., & de Vreese, C. H. (2019). *News framing effect*. New York: Routledge.

McCombs, M. E. (2004). *Setting the agenda: The mass media and public opinion*. Malden, MA: Polity Press.

McCombs, M. E., & Reynolds, A. (2002). News influence on our pictures of the world. In J. Bryant & M. B. Oliver (Eds.), *Media effects: Advances in theory and research*. New York: Routledge.

McCombs, M. E., & Shaw, D. L. (1972). The agenda-setting function of mass media. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 36(2), 176-187.

McGregor, J. (2010). Restating news values: Contemporary criteria for selecting the news. *Praxis*, Massey University. <http://praxis.massey.ac.nz/fileadmin/praxis/papers/JMcGregorp>

McQuail, D. (2010). *McQuail's mass communication theory (6th ed.)*. London: Sage.

Owuamalam, E. (2012). *Data analysis and research project writing*. Owerri: Top Class Agencies Ltd.

Oyovbaire, S. E. (1987). *The context of democracy in Nigeria*. Benin: Omega Publishers.

Rogers, E., & Dearing, J. (1988). Agenda setting research: Where has it been, and where is it going? *Communication Yearbook*, 11, 555-594.

Rubin, R. B., Rubin, A. M., & Piele, L. J. (2005). *Communication research: Strategies and sources (6th ed.)*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.

Scheufele, D. A., & Iyenga, S. (2014). The state of framing research: A call for new directions. In K. Kenski & K. H. Jamieson (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of political communication*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199793471.013.47>

Tewksbury, D., & Scheufele, D. A. (2009). News framing theory and research. In J. Bryant & M. B. Oliver (Eds.), *Media effects: Advances in theory and research (3rd ed.)*. New York, NY: Routledge.

Michigan International Journal of Marketing, New Media and Communication

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836-9424

Impact Factor: 6.39

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJMNMC>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Ugwuanyi, C. J., Olijó, I. I., & Verlumun, C. G. (2019). Social media as tools for political views expressed in the visuals shared among social media users. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2595>

Uzochukwu, C. E., & Ikegbunam, P. C. (2022). Analysis of newspapers' coverage of World Cancer Day: A study of select newspapers in Nigeria. *Journal of Media and Communication Studies*, 14(4), 79-91. <https://doi.org/10.58977/JMCS2022.0781>

Van Dijk, T. A. (2005). Opinions and ideologies in the press. In A. Bell & P. Garrett (Eds.), *Approaches to media discourse* (pp. 21-63). Malden, MA: Blackwell.

Yildiz, A., Guzel, O., & Yildiz, M. (2022). Media representation of Covid-19 pandemic and its impact on Australian hospitality businesses. *Anatolia: An International Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13032917.2022.2109051>

Zelizer, B. (1993). Journalists as interpretive communities. *Critical Studies in Mass Communication*, 10, 219-237. Speech Communication Association.